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POLICY BRIEF

**REGIONAL IMPACTS OF CLIMATE CHANGE AND THE
IMPORTANCE OF BIOECONOMICS IN PRESERVING THE
AMAZON RAINFOREST**

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REGIONAL IMPACTS OF CLIMATE CHANGE AND THE IMPORTANCE OF BIOECONOMICS IN PRESERVING THE AMAZON RAINFOREST

Could valuing the standing forest contribute to a new development model for the Amazon? One of the biggest challenges for conservation in the Amazon comes from the economic pressure exerted by sectors directly involved in exploiting natural resources in this territory. Historically, the region has been marked by a violent process of land occupation, resulting in conflicts, irregular ownership, illegal activities, and the rise of organized crime. Knowledge of the value of the standing forest helps raise funds that can be earmarked for public policies because preservation is currently becoming more important for the development of the new bioeconomy; the forest plays a fundamental role in mitigating risks related to global warming, and there is market interest in new investments related to environmental compensation.

The importance of preservation for the development of a new bioeconomy must be considered. According to a World Bank report published in May 2023, the estimated value of the Amazon rainforest is equivalent to US\$317 billion. Although the value is calculated, it isn't easy to project, considering the infinite applications of biodiversity for the bioeconomy. The Amazon is home to around 25% of global biodiversity, providing raw materials for sectors such as biotechnology, chemicals, food, fuels, and others and giving subsistence for rural populations.

The role of the forest in mitigating climate risks is gaining relevance in a scenario in which rising global temperatures have resulted in severe droughts, water shortages, fires, and crop losses. The moisture produced by the Amazon rainforest plays a fundamental role in atmospheric dynamics, being the source of "flying rivers," a phenomenon that favors the formation of rainfall, contributing to water supply, agriculture, and hydroelectric power generation throughout South America.

(...) we recommend investment in technology and the development of new sectors associated with the bioeconomy, which could reduce economic dependence on commodities and consequently reduce the pressure to expand the agricultural frontier, thereby reducing deforestation.

In general, forests are fundamental to mitigating the effects of climate change, acting as the main element of the biota capable of fixing carbon, removing around 36% of anthropogenic CO₂ emissions from the atmosphere, which the Amazon rainforest contributes 20% of the terrestrial biota's sink.

Access to investments linked to environmental preservation and reducing deforestation still needs to be improved and easier to access. International agreements and environmental laws have motivated compensation actions, donations for forest preservation (such as the Amazon Fund), and sustainable market mechanisms, including Brazil's efforts to implement carbon pricing. We can also highlight the work of the BNDES (National Bank for Economic and Social Development) in partnership with companies, which made 71 million euros available to implement the pilot project "Raízes da Amazônia" (Roots of the Amazon), aimed at land regularization and the development of the bioeconomy in agrarian reform settlements in Amapá.

In this sense, the valuation of the standing forest, justified by its environmental, social, and economic importance, reveals new development possibilities for Brazil, especially for the Amazon region, in addition to a new approach to raising international funds. The existence of new ways of raising funds for preservation and combating deforestation could have a positive impact on reducing CO₂ emissions, helping to mitigate climate risks. Finally, we recommend investment in technology and the development of new sectors associated with the bioeconomy, which could reduce economic dependence on commodities and consequently reduce the pressure to expand the agricultural frontier, thereby reducing deforestation.

THE ROLE OF THE AMAZON FOREST IN CLIMATE REGULATION IN BRAZIL

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